

Finance-Growth Nexus: Evidence from Systemically Important Islamic Finance Countries

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the relationship between financial development and economic growth in countries with systemically important Islamic finance. For this purpose, we use a number of estimation methods using the sample of 25 countries and covering the period of 2000-2019. Our findings show that financial development – at least as understood from the literature so far – may not be a significant factor in determining economic growth of a country. Perhaps, there is a need to find better measures for financial development as the most commonly used ones (private credit, liquid liabilities and broad money) are shown to be insignificant. These results are robust across different estimation specifications and methods used.

JEL classification: C33, F43, G2, O1, O4, P52,

Keywords: financial development, economic growth, Islamic finance, finance-growth nexus.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

An efficient and functional financial market is considered an indispensable ingredient for overall economic growth even though its impact on economic growth and stability is far from being conclusive. The evidence reported in the literature on the finance-growth nexus provide four general views: (i) *supply-leading* – development of financial sector leads to economic growth (Bittencourt, 2012; Goldsmith, 1969; Gurley & Shaw, 1955; McKinnon, 1973; Patrick, 1966; Porter, 1966; Schumpeter, 1912); (2) *demand-following* – economic growth leads to development of financial sector (Al-Yousif, 2002; Robinson, 1952); (3) *bidirectional relationship* – development of financial sector leads to economic growth and economic growth in turn contributes to the financial development (Demetriades & Hussein, 1996; Greenwood & Smith, 1997); and (4) *no relationship* – no causal relationship between finance and economic growth (Lucas, 1988).¹

Empirically, the importance of banking sector development as a catalyst for economic growth has been given predominant emphasis, in great part due to the fact that the banking sector forms a main component of the financial sector especially in developing countries. Banks provide a number of financial services needed for well-functioning of a financial system such as mobilization and allocation of financial resources, identification of investment opportunities, facilitating trading and diversification of risk, and information processing that may lead to a decrease in the transaction cost and asymmetric information problems as well as improvement

¹ Al-Yousif (2002) finds support for all these views. He used both time series and panel data and the results varied due to use of different variables. Similar findings are reported by Demetriades and Hussein (1996). A short summary is provided by Prochniak and Wasiaik (2017).

in the corporate governance mechanisms, which are reasons underlying the *supply-leading* view (Schumpeter, (1912); Gurley and Shaw, (1955); Goldsmith, (1969); and McKinnon, (1973).

Although the view has received much support since the publication of King and Levine's (1993) paper, the global financial crisis has brought in the fore the skepticism of at best the qualified view on the positive effect of banking sector development on economic growth. Such studies as Favara (2003), Rioja & Valev (2004), Shen & Lee (2006), Arcand, Berkes, & Panizza (2012) and Law & Singh (2014) suggest that there might be limits to benefits of finance.

Given its relative resilience to the global financial crisis, the Islamic finance industry (IFI) attracted a lot of attention in last decade. Consequently, the global assets of the IFI grew to about US\$ 2.5 trillion in 2018 and it is projected to grow to about \$3.47 trillion by 2024 with a projected growth of 6%, a growth rate that is far higher than the conventional financial industry's annual growth rate (Deloitte, 2019). Nevertheless, the share of IFI in the global finance is insignificant (ICD-REFINITIV, 2018; IFSB, 2019). According to the Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB), there are 13 systemically important Islamic finance jurisdictions² although, in our study we are going to include more jurisdictions.

However, despite overwhelming literature on finance–growth nexus in general, this issue has not been adequately addressed within the countries with a growing market share of IFI. To the best of our knowledge, we did not come across a study focusing on this sample countries that may offer unique characteristics. This motivated us to investigate this relationship within these countries. Besides, majority of studies are primarily focused on developed economies while ignoring developing ones. The sample countries with their Islamic finance exposure offer new avenue for investigation of this relationship. Furthermore, recent studies indicate no significant impact of financial development on economic growth as this finance-growth nexus is fading in recent years (Ali, Ibrahim, & Shah; Rousseau & Wachtel, 2011). We want to see whether the financial liberalization and introduction of Islamic finance practices in recent years added value to the overall economic growth via financial development improvement (if any).

Having said that, the main objective of this paper is to remedy these issues through analysis of the existing literature and contribution to this growing area of research by exploring the impact of financial development on economic growth within countries with systemically important Islamic finance. Using a panel dataset of 25 countries and covering the period of 2000-2019, we will therefore test the following hypotheses:

H₀: There is a positive relationship between financial development and economic growth

H₁: There is a negative or no relation between financial development and economic growth

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a literature review; Section 3 describes the data and methodology used; Section 4 analyses empirical results; and Section 5 is left for concluding remarks.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

The interaction and relationship between financial development and economic growth has a long history. A discussion on the topic was initiated by Schumpeter (1912) and further elaborated theoretically by Robinson (1952), Goldsmith (1969), Shaw (1973), and Lucas

² According to the report, countries with Islamic banking assets representing more than 15% of their total domestic banking sector assets are considered systemically important. Countries with this level of banking market share are Iran, Sudan, Brunei, Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Malaysia, Qatar, UAE, Bangladesh, Djibouti, Jordan, Palestine and Bahrain (IFSB, 2019, pp. 10-11).

(1988). This led to a number of empirical studies that investigated this relationship and looked for empirical evidences in order to support original economic theories.

Two papers by Levine (1997, 2003) provide extensive overviews of the finance–growth nexus literature. In the first paper, Levine (1997) found positive impact of financial sector development on long–run economic growth. In the second paper, evidence point out to the fact that better–developed financial structures – represented by the size of banking system and the liquidity of stock markets – experience faster growth rates Levine (2003).

Based on theoretical foundations laid down by Goldsmith (1969) and Shaw (1973), a number of authors found a positive contribution of finance on growth and this is the most commonly accepted and confirmed view in the literature (Ahmed & Ansari, 1998; Beck, Degryse, & Kneer, 2014; Beck, Levine, & Loayza, 2000; Christopoulos & Tsionas, 2004; King & Levine, 1993; Levine, Loayza, & Beck, 2000; Rajan & Zingales, 1998; Seetanah, Ramessur, & Rojid, 2009). Not only that there is a positive relationship between finance and growth but also financial depth and growth (Christopoulos & Tsionas, 2004; Guiso et al., 2004; Seetanah et al., 2009). Furthermore, studies also indicate that a well–developed legal system, accounting standards (Levine et al., 2000), investment, openness, education, macroeconomic stability and institutional development (Bittencourt, 2012; Seetanah et al., 2009) contribute to the development of financial intermediaries. Nevertheless, while a large theoretical and empirical literature shows the importance and impact of finance on growth, its benefits are not equally shared by all countries. In particular, region, income level and a type of economy affect the impact of financial deepening (Barajas, Chami, & Yousefi, 2013).

In addition, according to some empirical results, there is a non-linear relationship between finance and growth. In line with those studies, the development of finance initially contributes to economic growth. However, as it reaches a threshold point, financial development becomes detrimental to economic growth. Hence, these studies indicate that there is an ‘optimal’ level of financial development for it to have positive impact on economic growth. Simply having ‘more’ of financial development may not be the best approach (Law & Singh, 2014; Prochniak & Wasiak, 2017).

Contrary to general view about the finance–growth relationship that can be find in the literature, there are a number of studies showing different results. For example, De Gregorio and Guidotti (1995), Fernandez and Galetovic (1994), Luintel and Khan (1999), Ram (1999), Andersen and Tarp (2003), Favara (2003), Naceur and Ghazouani (2007), Hsueh et al. (2013) and (Carré & L’œillet, 2018) show that the direction of causality between financial development and economic growth is sensitive to the financial development indicators, econometric techniques and sample period used. Thus, a negative relationship is found in number of studies (Andersen & Tarp, 2003; Khan, 2001; Luintel & Khan, 1999).

Finally, Lucas (1988) claims that the development of financial system is insignificant in affecting economic growth indicating no causal relationship between finance and growth. Al–Yousif (2002) finds support for all these views briefly explained above. He used both time series and panel data and the results varied due to use of different variables. Similar findings are reported by Demetriades and Hussein (1996) and a short summary is provided by Prochniak and Wasiak (2017). Finally, as if the current discussion did not create enough confusion, there are also studies that find more than one relationship in their samples [Hsueh et al. \(2013\)](#) (Halkos & Trigoni, 2010; Hassan, Sanchez, & Yu, 2011; Marques, Fuinhas, & Marques, 2013).

It seems that the debate on the finance–growth nexus is non-fading and additional investigations on the topic may provide additional explanations and insights. Taking this into consideration together with the fact that there is a lack of studies focusing on the sample countries and the

increasing importance of Islamic finance worldwide, it is believed that this study will provide valuable findings for all stakeholders and add to the existing body of literature.

3.0 DATA, MODEL AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data and Sample Selection

This study employs panel data techniques using annual time series data of the selected macroeconomic indicators of 25 countries with systemically important Islamic finance industry. The countries covered are Afghanistan, Bahrain, Bangladesh, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Brunei Darussalam, Djibouti, Egypt, Indonesia, Iran, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Malaysia, Maldives, Oman, Pakistan, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Senegal, Sudan, Tunisia, Turkey, United Arab Emirates, West Bank and Gaza (Palestine) and Yemen.³

All data are sourced from the World Bank's database and cover the period of 2000-2019, making it a total of 20 years. As we are covering 20-year period and 25 countries (cross-sectional units), there should be 500 observation in total (20 x 25). However, as a number of countries reported no data the total number of observations for each country is not the same. Hence, we are dealing with an unbalanced panel.

Following the existing literature, this study uses the real per capita GDP growth (GDP) as a measure for the economic growth. The literature, however, does not offer a consensus concerning a financial development measure. As pointed out briefly in the introduction, the results differ significantly due to indicator(s) used as proxy for financial development. Consequently, many authors use several proxies for the financial development measure or opt for a sort of index based on a number of proxies (Carré & L'œillet, 2018). Some authors use different measures for robustness results, while others are forced to use certain measures due to availability of data especially in panel data analysis covering countries with different levels of financial development (for instance, markets dominated by banks as opposed to those with a well-developed stock markets) (Valickova, Havranek, & Horvath, 2015).

In line with this brief explanation and the existing literature, we use three indicators of financial development: (i) a ratio of credit to the private sector provided by financial intermediaries as a percentage of GDP (PR). This measures the efficiency of funds channeling to the private sector (Al-Malkawi & Abdullah, 2011; Levine, 1997); (ii) a ratio of liquid liabilities to GDP (LL) that measures the financial sector size and depth. It also represents banks' ability to mobilize funds (Compton & Giedeman, 2011; King & Levine, 1993; Law & Singh, 2014; Levine, 1997); (iii) a ratio of broad money supply (M3) to GDP that measures financial sector size. The use of M3 is seen more appropriate for countries in which money is primarily used as store of value (Hassan et al., 2011; Valickova et al., 2015).⁴

As for control variables, we use a number of macroeconomic variables to control their impacts on economic growth as the literature point out to their significance in determining economic growth. In particular, we use gross capital formation (GCF), trade openness (TO), human

³ Although, the IFSB report indicates 12+1 countries (Iran, Sudan, Brunei, Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Malaysia, Qatar, UAE, Bangladesh, Djibouti, Jordan and Palestine + Bahrain) that are withing 15% share in the total banking assets in respective countries, we included the other countries from the report that have more than 3% share in the total banking assets for a sake of this study. We will, however, run robustness tests on the original 13 countries later on.

⁴ Due to non-availability of sufficient data on stock market development in majority of countries we did not include it as an indicator of financial development in above model.

capital (HC), bank cost to income ratio (BCI), inflation rate (I), and the financial crisis dummy (C).

The GCF is a control variable that reflects the overall economic development of a country (Levine & Renelt, 1992). The TO, measured as the sum of exports and imports of goods and services as a share of GDP, represents the current economic activities of a country (Beck et al., 2014; Bist, 2018). The HC, proxied by the total labor force comprising of people ages 15 and older, measures the human capital accumulation and it is one of the pillars of the economic development theory. The BCI measures overhead costs relative to gross revenues with higher ratios indicating lower levels of cost efficiency. It is argued that bank efficiency and its stability promote economic growth (Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt, & Merrouche, 2013). The financial crisis dummy (C) is used as an indicator of macroeconomic development. It takes the value of one for the year 2008 and 2009 and zero otherwise to capture the effect of the global financial crisis on economic growth. During a financial crisis, banks are faced with a number of challenges that make them fragile. This brings about uncertainty in the market and increases overall risk. Likewise, inflation is used as a proxy for monetary (in)stability. It affects not only growth but also financial activities within a country through its direct impact on the interest rates. High inflationary countries are faced with generally underdeveloped financial systems that are prone to financial crises (Bist, 2018).

3.2 Model and Methods Used

To assess the impact of the financial development on economic growth in systemically important Islamic finance countries we employ the following panel data model:

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha FD_{it} + \beta X_{it} + \mu_i + \eta_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where GDP_{it} is the real per capita GDP; FD_{it} represents a measure of financial development; X_{it} is a vector of all control variables; μ_i is a country-specific effect; η_t is a time-specific effect; ε_{it} is a random error term that captures all other variables; and where i denotes the cross-sectional dimension (i.e., country) and t denotes the time dimension (i.e., year). Due to the presence of non-linearity in growth equations, and in line with prevailing literature, we transfer all variables (except financial crisis) in logarithmic form (Naceur, Blotvogel, Fischer, & Shi, 2017).

The literature is overwhelmed with various estimation methods that have been used in analyzing the finance-growth nexus. Different methods, as well as different indicators and samples, led to different conclusions. In this particular case, we are going to apply a number of estimation methods. Following the literature (Seetanah et al., 2009; Shen & Lee, 2006) and due to the availability of data, the study will apply the pooled OLS (POLS), the fixed effects (FE) and the random effects (RE) models. From Equation 1 above, we will test for random effects using the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test. The null hypothesis in the LM test is that variances across entities is zero. This is, no significant difference across units (i.e., no panel effect). Rejecting the null gives support to RE estimation method.

Taking step further, the FE model refers to the case when μ_i and η_t are treated as fixed parameters. On the contrary, when they are treated as random variables with zero means and constant variance, then we are referring to the RE model. Furthermore, to choose which model, the FE or the RE estimator, fits the data better, we use the Hausman test which assumes that there is no difference between the two models' estimates (H_0). Rejecting the null hypothesis indicates superiority of the FE estimator, otherwise we should go for the RE estimator.

However, as a number of studies indicated biased and inconsistent results in the FE and RE estimation methods (Nickell, 1981), we also provide estimation based on the Least Squares

Dummy Variables estimator (LSDV). Nevertheless, Kiviet (1995), Bruno (2005a, 2005b) and Bun and Carree (2006) showed that LSDV and GMM panel data estimators suffer from inconsistency and finite-sample biases. Hence, we turn to the bias-corrected LSDV estimator (LSDVC) initialized by Anderson and Hsiao (1982), as our preferred estimation strategy, where it uses the second lag of dependent variable (in differenced or level form) as an instrument. Finally, the generalized methods of moments (GMM) method will be used for robustness results.

4.0 EMPIRICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis: An Overview

First of all, it is important to note here that due to a potentially non-linear relationship between economic growth and control variables, and in line with prevailing literature, we transform all control variables (except crisis) into natural logarithm forms. Hence, we will use these variables in natural logarithm forms throughout the study (Naceur et al., 2017).

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in this study. The average economic growth of the sample countries is positive and relatively stable. Private credit, as a proxy of financial development, has a relatively higher variations as compared to the other two proxies, namely liquid liability and broad money.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
GDP per capita	457	1.881	4.872	-15.397	50.236
Private credit	457	41.123	26.533	1.266	127.232
Liquid liabilities	412	54.392	27.515	8.968	135.12
Broad money	454	59.414	27.992	11	140.092
Trade openness	432	86.803	46.991	19.101	304.329
Gross capital formation	417	24.356	7.046	2.855	48.869
Bank cost to income	396	47.825	14.83	22.683	139.468
Human capital	457	16114739	26755709	90256	1.348e+08
Inflation	457	7.124	10.25	-26.1	52.924

4.2 Results and Discussion

Table 2, Table 3, and Table 4 present the estimated results of Eq(1) using private credit, liquid liabilities and broad money as proxies for the financial development measure, respectively. In each table, the pooled ordinary least square (POLs), the random effect (RE), the fixed effect (FE), the least square dummy variable (LSDV) and the bias-corrected least square dummy variable (LSDVC) methods were used to estimate the results. Each estimator consists of two estimations. The first column is considering the main independent variable and all control variables except the crisis dummy. The second column is including the crisis dummy to see the effect of the recent global financial crisis (GFC) 2008-2009 on economic growth. Given the fact that the sample is covering the countries with a significant share of the Islamic finance industry (IFI) and that it has been argued that the IFI showed a degree of resilience to the GFC, it would be interesting to see how these countries performed during these trouble years. Ever since the GFC, this topic has been scrutinized by researchers, and the results are far from being conclusive (Ibrahim, 2015).

In general, based on the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier (LM) test, it is evident that RE model is to be preferred to POLs as there is evidence of significant differences across countries. To determine whether to use FE or RE, we run the Hausman test and its results depend on the

proxy used for the financial development measure. FE is preferred in case of private credit only while RE is preferred in case of liquid liabilities and broad money at 5% significance level. Finally, given the overall superiority of the LSDVC estimator, we will base our interpretation primarily on these results, although for a comparative purposes we may refer to other estimators as well.

In particular, Table 2 shows conflicting results. Our main focus variable, financial development as measured by private credit, is decreasing economic growth when POLS, RE, FE and LSDV estimators are used, although it is insignificant under FE model. In contrast, it is insignificant with a positive sign in case of LSDVC. These results remain consistent even after adding the financial crisis dummy variable. The results from Table 3 and Table 4 where liquid liabilities and broad money are used as proxies for the financial development measure are more consistent. In both cases, results show that majority of our main variables are not significantly associated with economic growth in the sample countries. As a reason for this insignificance, Rousseau and Wachtel (2011) mentioned the overall weakening of the finance-growth nexus. It seems that financial liberalization taking place in developing countries (to which majority of our sample countries belong) is not accompanied with the required expertise to make this process smooth. Consequently, this untackled issue is causing instabilities in the market making financial development less effective in generating desired growth. Another reason could be attributed to the low level of financial development in the sample countries as the average is 41.13%.

In short, based on the estimation results from all three tables, it is evident that financial development – proxied by private credit, liquid liabilities and broad money – has no significant impact on economic growth in sample countries with systemically important share of the Islamic finance industry. Significantly negative impact of financial development on economic growth that is reported under POLS, RE and LSDV estimators in Table 2 and RE estimator in Table 3 and Table 4 need to be taken with a great caution as these estimations lead to biasness and inconsistency in estimation results as mentioned earlier. Hence, we rely on the results provided by the LSDVC estimators which show insignificant effect of financial development on economic growth.

The lagged dependent variable is the only variable that is significant in all three tables across all the specifications. The coefficient has a relatively stable impact on economic growth ranging from 0.278 in case of broad money to 0.291 in case of liquid liabilities. Similarly, the trade openness is significantly contributing to the economic growth only in Table 3 where liquid liability proxy is used. Rajan and Zingales (1998) and Law and Singh (2014) reported similar findings. However, when it comes to other control variables, it seems that majority of them have no significant impact on economic growth under the LSDVC estimator.⁵ As for crisis dummy, its results are consistent under all estimators and they show that the crisis decreases economic growth significantly in the case of our sample countries. This may be caused by a fact that these economies opened their financial markets and underwent a great deal of financial liberalization to cater for different and growing needs of its customers. This led to the development of Islamic finance products and services without a proper supervision and regulation. Furthermore, this financial liberalization and openness led to a greater internationalization of their markets that made them vulnerable to financial crises. At the same time, the inherent stability of IFI may not be realized yet and the current market share of IFI in these countries may not offer diversification and stability benefits as it is theoretically argued. This is in line with study by Shahzad, Ferrer, Ballester, and Umar (2017) who reject the decoupling hypothesis as the Islamic stock market offer no diversification benefits to investors.

⁵ The results are pretty much same with all other estimators as well in most cases.

Table 2: The impact of financial development on economic growth: Private credit

VARIABLES	(1) POLS	(2) POLS	(3) RE	(4) RE	(5) FE	(6) FE	(7) LSDV	(8) LSDV	(9) LSDVC	(10) LSDVC
Private credit	-0.061** (0.024)	-0.062*** (0.024)	-0.075** (0.033)	-0.079** (0.033)	-0.021 (0.059)	-0.021 (0.059)	-0.053** (0.024)	-0.053** (0.024)	0.039 (0.069)	0.039 (0.069)
Trade openness	0.058 (0.046)	0.060 (0.045)	0.078 (0.063)	0.087 (0.063)	0.222* (0.115)	0.222* (0.115)	0.046 (0.045)	0.046 (0.045)	0.124 (0.112)	0.124 (0.112)
Gross capital formation	-0.001 (0.056)	0.004 (0.056)	-0.014 (0.065)	-0.006 (0.064)	-0.039 (0.073)	-0.039 (0.073)	-0.019 (0.056)	-0.019 (0.056)	-0.022 (0.096)	-0.022 (0.096)
Bank cost to income	0.129** (0.059)	0.122** (0.059)	0.024 (0.078)	-0.001 (0.078)	-0.159 (0.105)	-0.159 (0.105)	0.151** (0.059)	0.151** (0.059)	-0.162 (0.134)	-0.162 (0.134)
Human capital	0.035*** (0.012)	0.036*** (0.012)	0.032* (0.020)	0.034* (0.020)	-0.166 (0.102)	-0.166 (0.102)	0.038*** (0.012)	0.038*** (0.012)	-0.102 (0.089)	-0.102 (0.089)
Inflation	0.065* (0.034)	0.053 (0.034)	0.062* (0.034)	0.047 (0.033)	-0.010 (0.042)	-0.010 (0.042)	-0.006 (0.041)	-0.006 (0.041)	-0.019 (0.057)	-0.019 (0.057)
Crisis (dummy)		-0.156*** (0.050)		-0.163*** (0.047)		-0.338*** (0.103)		-0.354*** (0.104)		-0.284* (0.148)
GDP per capita _(t-1)									0.279*** (0.056)	0.279*** (0.056)
Constant	1.553*** (0.480)	1.613*** (0.475)	2.016*** (0.635)	2.108*** (0.636)	5.339*** (1.564)	5.339*** (1.564)	1.835*** (0.487)	1.835*** (0.487)		
Year dummies	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	348	348
R-squared	0.089	0.114	0.309	0.267	0.320	0.320	0.177	0.177		
No of countries	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
Significance of model	5.875***	6.569***	13.945**	25.660***	2.303***	2.303***	3.202***	3.202***		
Breusch-Pagan LM test			12.984***	14.998***						
Hausman test					20.131***	16.172**				
Model degrees of freedom	6	7	6	7	6	7	23	23		

Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10

Table 3: The impact of financial development on economic growth: Liquid liabilities

VARIABLES	(1) POLS	(2) POLS	(3) RE	(4) RE	(5) FE	(6) FE	(7) LSDV	(8) LSDV	(9) LSDVC	(10) LSDVC
Liquid liabilities	-0.033 (0.040)	-0.043 (0.040)	-0.090 (0.057)	-0.113* (0.058)	-0.038 (0.102)	-0.069 (0.100)	-0.023 (0.041)	-0.023 (0.041)	-0.042 (0.153)	-0.042 (0.153)
Trade openness	0.017 (0.049)	0.023 (0.048)	0.054 (0.067)	0.074 (0.067)	0.138 (0.102)	0.183* (0.100)	0.005 (0.049)	0.005 (0.049)	0.174** (0.081)	0.174** (0.081)
Gross capital formation	-0.021 (0.055)	-0.018 (0.054)	-0.037 (0.063)	-0.030 (0.062)	-0.004 (0.072)	0.007 (0.070)	-0.038 (0.055)	-0.038 (0.055)	-0.003 (0.097)	-0.003 (0.097)
Bank cost to income	0.142** (0.059)	0.134** (0.058)	0.024 (0.077)	-0.002 (0.077)	-0.173* (0.103)	-0.206** (0.101)	0.167*** (0.059)	0.167*** (0.059)	-0.145 (0.108)	-0.145 (0.108)
Human capital	0.030** (0.012)	0.031** (0.012)	0.027 (0.020)	0.029 (0.020)	-0.085 (0.074)	-0.089 (0.072)	0.033*** (0.012)	0.033*** (0.012)	-0.101 (0.138)	-0.101 (0.138)
Inflation	0.062* (0.034)	0.048 (0.034)	0.054 (0.034)	0.037 (0.034)	0.045 (0.036)	0.024 (0.035)	-0.009 (0.041)	-0.009 (0.041)	-0.017 (0.036)	-0.017 (0.036)
Crisis (dummy)		-0.154*** (0.049)		-0.168*** (0.047)		-0.185*** (0.046)		-0.065 (0.099)		-0.273*** (0.086)
GDP per capita _(t-1)									0.291*** (0.071)	0.291*** (0.071)
Constant	1.754*** (0.482)	1.831*** (0.477)	2.385*** (0.641)	2.513*** (0.641)	4.239*** (1.157)	4.421*** (1.132)	1.982*** (0.488)	1.982*** (0.488)		
Year dummies	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	361	361	361	361	361	361	361	361	344	344
R-squared	0.074	0.099	0.161	0.113	0.234	0.269	0.159	0.159		
No of countries	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
Significance of model	4.718***	5.547***	9.610	22.433***	1.797*	3.874***	2.778***	2.778***		
Breusch-Pagan LM test			13.435***	16.425***						
Hausman test					10.396	13.670*				
Model degrees of freedom	6	7	6	7	6	7	23	23		

Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10

Table 4: The impact of financial development on economic growth: Broad money

VARIABLES	(1) POLS	(2) POLS	(3) RE	(4) RE	(5) FE	(6) FE	(7) LSDV	(8) LSDV	(9) LSDVC	(10) LSDVC
Broad money	-0.050 (0.040)	-0.056 (0.039)	-0.107* (0.058)	-0.123** (0.059)	-0.068 (0.100)	-0.083 (0.098)	-0.032 (0.040)	-0.032 (0.040)	-0.001 (0.169)	-0.001 (0.169)
Trade openness	0.037 (0.048)	0.041 (0.047)	0.082 (0.066)	0.098 (0.067)	0.198* (0.102)	0.241** (0.100)	0.021 (0.047)	0.021 (0.047)	0.150 (0.122)	0.150 (0.122)
Gross capital formation	-0.033 (0.056)	-0.029 (0.055)	-0.039 (0.063)	-0.030 (0.063)	-0.002 (0.072)	0.008 (0.071)	-0.048 (0.055)	-0.048 (0.055)	-0.016 (0.104)	-0.016 (0.104)
Bank cost to income	0.142** (0.060)	0.135** (0.059)	0.037 (0.078)	0.011 (0.078)	-0.144 (0.103)	-0.183* (0.102)	0.167*** (0.059)	0.167*** (0.059)	-0.160 (0.143)	-0.160 (0.143)
Human capital	0.034*** (0.013)	0.035*** (0.012)	0.034* (0.020)	0.036* (0.021)	-0.078 (0.069)	-0.085 (0.068)	0.036*** (0.012)	0.036*** (0.012)	-0.102 (0.098)	-0.102 (0.098)
Inflation	0.065* (0.035)	0.052 (0.035)	0.059* (0.034)	0.043 (0.034)	0.049 (0.036)	0.029 (0.036)	-0.006 (0.041)	-0.006 (0.041)	-0.022 (0.056)	-0.022 (0.056)
Crisis (dummy)		-0.156*** (0.050)		-0.167*** (0.047)		-0.186*** (0.047)		-0.346*** (0.105)		-0.273** (0.121)
GDP per capita _(t-1)									0.278*** (0.055)	0.278*** (0.055)
Constant	1.690*** (0.488)	1.761*** (0.483)	2.168*** (0.645)	2.282*** (0.647)	3.861*** (1.122)	4.052*** (1.099)	1.929*** (0.493)	1.929*** (0.493)		
Year dummies	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	348	348
R-squared	0.077	0.101	0.210	0.155	0.237	0.271	0.166	0.166		
No of countries	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
Significance of model	5.018***	5.791***	11.893*	24.223***	2.114*	4.125***	2.975***	2.975***		
Breusch-Pagan LM test			15.732***	18.458***						
Hausman test					10.047	10.047				
Model degrees of freedom	6	7	6	7	6	7	23	23		

Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10

4.3 Robustness Tests

As for robustness tests, we opt for the GMM estimators. Table 5 provide estimation results for difference and system GMM estimators using private credit, liquid liabilities and broad money as the main focus variables. Our earlier results, using LSDVC estimator as the most suitable method for the estimation in this case, are confirmed using the GMM estimators. All our focus variables are found to have negative, yet insignificant effect on economic growth using system GMM which is considered superior as compared to difference GMM estimators under which these variables are found to be significant. Lagged dependent and crisis variables are found to have significant effect on economic growth – positive and negative respectively. All other control variables are in line with previously reported results.

All in all, using a number of estimation methods and in particular the LSDVC estimator that is found to be the superior for the dynamic panel data such as the current one, this study finds no evidence of significant effect of financial development on economic growth. These results are supported by using three proxies for financial development – private credit, liquid liability and broad money – that lead to the same results. In addition, robustness tests using GMM estimators are also in conformity with the main results. It seems that finance-growth nexus link is fading as pointed out by Rousseau and Wachtel (2011). In addition, given the rapid growth of financial industry in the sample countries and recent growth of the Islamic finance industry, its services and products coupled with financial deregulation that has not been sufficiently addressed, the effects of financial development may have been diluted. At the same time, we may want to explore new proxies for financial development that may explain the finance-growth nexus in a better and more efficient way.

Table 5: The impact of financial development on economic growth: Robustness tests

VARIABLES	(1) Diff GMM	(2) Diff GMM	(3) Sys GMM	(4) Sys GMM	(5) Diff GMM	(6) Diff GMM	(7) Sys GMM	(8) Sys GMM	(9) Diff GMM	(10) Diff GMM	(11) Sys GMM	(12) Sys GMM
GDP per capita _(t-1)	0.185 (0.182)	0.203 (0.182)	0.454*** (0.155)	0.577*** (0.162)	0.361* (0.195)	0.224* (0.132)	0.469*** (0.172)	0.560*** (0.149)	0.353* (0.194)	0.114 (0.107)	0.455*** (0.165)	0.551*** (0.160)
Private credit	-0.272* (0.142)	-0.295** (0.142)	-0.024 (0.019)	-0.008 (0.018)								
Liquid liabilities					-0.622*** (0.206)	-0.678*** (0.186)	-0.018 (0.038)	-0.027 (0.043)				
Broad money									-0.757*** (0.204)	-0.733*** (0.164)	-0.014 (0.034)	-0.007 (0.043)
Trade openness	-0.143 (0.171)	-0.043 (0.172)	-0.005 (0.047)	0.036 (0.079)	-0.264 (0.195)	-0.174 (0.178)	-0.012 (0.059)	0.022 (0.047)	-0.296 (0.189)	-0.190 (0.162)	-0.020 (0.054)	0.005 (0.087)
Gross capital formation	0.185 (0.152)	0.210 (0.152)	0.129** (0.062)	0.105 (0.075)	0.232 (0.168)	0.246 (0.151)	0.106* (0.056)	0.066 (0.049)	0.260 (0.162)	0.230* (0.135)	0.106* (0.057)	0.073 (0.095)
Bank cost to income	0.060 (0.151)	0.001 (0.151)	0.024 (0.079)	0.159 (0.100)	0.148 (0.171)	0.048 (0.152)	0.043 (0.075)	0.116* (0.069)	0.109 (0.164)	-0.004 (0.139)	0.039 (0.078)	0.126 (0.138)
Human capital	-0.014 (0.147)	-0.009 (0.147)	0.015 (0.017)	0.017 (0.020)	0.140 (0.146)	0.089 (0.122)	0.013 (0.016)	0.009 (0.011)	0.177 (0.144)	0.069 (0.104)	0.013 (0.017)	0.009 (0.023)
Inflation	0.048 (0.037)	0.039 (0.037)	0.046 (0.029)	0.062 (0.044)	0.031 (0.042)	0.013 (0.039)	0.050* (0.030)	0.059 (0.046)	0.025 (0.041)	0.011 (0.035)	0.049* (0.028)	0.057 (0.047)
Crisis (dummy)		-0.198*** (0.048)		-0.163*** (0.060)		-0.221*** (0.048)		-0.161*** (0.061)		-0.209*** (0.044)		-0.162** (0.063)
Constant			0.774** (0.378)	-0.316 (1.314)			0.768 (0.471)	0.290 (0.532)			0.849* (0.457)	0.247 (1.798)
Observations	324	324	348	348	320	320	344	344	324	324	348	348
No. of instruments	21	22	23	24	21	23	23	24	21	23	23	24
No. of groups	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
AR1 p-value	0.037	0.037	0.037	0.037	0.037	0.037	0.037	0.037	0.037	0.037	0.037	0.037
AR2 p-value	0.254	0.254	0.254	0.254	0.254	0.254	0.254	0.254	0.254	0.254	0.254	0.254
Hansen p-value	0.415	0.415	0.415	0.415	0.415	0.415	0.415	0.415	0.415	0.415	0.415	0.415

Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10

5.0 CONCLUSION

The present study was designed to investigate the effect of financial development on economic growth in countries with systemically important Islamic finance. Our findings suggest that financial development plays insignificant role on economic growth of the sample countries. These results, although counterintuitive, are consistent using different proxies and estimation methods. Our findings show that financial development – at least as understood from the literature so far – may not be a significant factor in determining economic growth of a country. Perhaps, there is a need to find better measures for financial development as the most commonly used ones (private credit, liquid liabilities and broad money) are shown to be insignificant. In addition, there might be other factors more important for economic growth than financial development that need to be properly addressed. In line with this, it would be interesting to investigate the impact of different aspects of financial development on economic growth. Besides, using updated dataset with additional or new set of variables may shed extra light on the topic and provide additional recommendations.

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